

Growth and Properties of Sb-Ge-Se Thin Films: A Promising Material for Sustainable Photovoltaic Devices Development

Víctor Bonal, Samira Khelifi, Sanja Djurdjić Mijin, Beatriz Galiana, Yudania Sánchez, Marina García-Pardo, Antonio Arranz, Nazaret Ruíz-Marín, Snežana Lazić, Rosalia Serna, and Raquel Caballero*

Sb-Ge chalcogenides are known as effective phase change materials, making them ideal for optical data storage applications, detectors, and sensors. However, there have been no photovoltaic devices developed using these materials to date. In this work, Sb-Ge-Se crystalline thin films with different [Sb]/[Ge] atomic ratios are successfully grown for the first time through the selenization of co-evaporated Sb and Ge layers. The impact of the Se addition and temperature during the selenization process on the composition, structural, morphological, vibrational, and optical properties of the Sb-Ge-Se layers is investigated. The coexistence of Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 has been confirmed using various characterization techniques, including Grazing Incidence X-ray diffraction, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy. Additionally, Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy has revealed Ge-enrichment regions surrounding the Sb_2Se_3 crystals. The composition of the co-evaporated film and final Ge content in the chalcogenide film govern the band gap energy, increasing from 1.41 to 1.83 eV. We present the inaugural operational SLG/Mo/Sb-Ge-Se/CdS/ZnO/ITO photovoltaic devices with a total efficiency of 1.34%. The primary factors limiting the device performance are the significant CdS diffusion into the active layer and the high defect density, as determined by Capacitance-Voltage and Drive-Level Capacitance Profiling. The devices exhibit excellent stability after 1 year of storage in ambient air. These first prototypes of Sb-Ge-Se crystalline thin films pave the way for advancement in the development of sustainable and stable photovoltaic devices.

1. Introduction

Low-dimensional $\text{Sb}_2(\text{S,Se})_3$ absorber used for photovoltaic (PV) devices has garnered significant interest over the past few years. Quasi-1D $\text{Sb}_2(\text{S,Se})_3$ exhibits a high absorption coefficient, a tunable bandgap energy E_g , ranging from 1.2 to 1.7 eV, and high stability. Additionally, it has a melting point that is considerably lower than that of CIGSe, CdTe, and CZTSSe, enabling processing at lower temperatures, and its constituents are earth-abundant.^[1] $\text{Sb}_2(\text{S,Se})_3$ -based solar cells have already demonstrated efficiencies exceeding 10%.^[2,3]

On the other hand, the 2D germanium monoselenide (GeSe) has also emerged as a promising photovoltaic absorber material due to its attractive optoelectronic properties such as a high absorption coefficient and p-type conductivity, as well as its non-toxic and earth-abundant constituents.^[4] Its direct band gap makes it more suitable for photovoltaic applications. Superstrate solar cells based on Ge-Se with $E_g = 1.24$ eV achieving an efficiency of 5.2% were previously reported.^[5] The challenge associated with the growth of a single Ge-Se phase material impedes the enhancement in the PV device performance, especially when

Dr. V. Bonal, Dr. S. Djurdjić Mijin, Dr. A. Arranz, Dr. S. Lazić
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Calle Francisco Tomás y Valiente 7,
28049, Madrid, Spain

Dr. S. Khelifi
Department of Solid-State Sciences, Ghent University, Krijgslaan 281, 9000,
Ghent, Belgium

Dr. S. Djurdjić Mijin
Institute of Physics Belgrade, University of Belgrade, Pregrevica 1118, 11080,
Belgrade, Serbia

Dr. B. Galiana
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Avda. Universidad 40, 28911 Leganés,
Madrid, Spain

Dr. Y. Sánchez
IREC, Catalonia Institute for Energy Research, C/Jardins de les Dones de
Negre 1, Barcelona 08930, Spain

Dr. M. García-Pardo, Prof. R. Serna, Dr. R. Caballero
Instituto de Óptica Daza de Valdés-CSIC, Calle Serrano 121, 28006, Madrid, Spain
E-mail: raquel.caballero@csic.es

Dr. N. Ruíz-Marín
University Research Institute on Electron Microscopy & Materials
(IMEYMAT), Universidad de Cádiz, 11510, Cádiz, Spain

Dr. S. Lazić
Condensed Matter Physics Center (IFIMAC), Universidad Autónoma de
Madrid, 28049, Madrid, Spain

Instituto Universitario de Ciencia de Materiales Nicolás Cabrera (INC),
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Calle Francisco Tomás y Valiente 7,
28049, Madrid, Spain

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/eem2.70059>.

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Table 1. Composition of the Sb-Ge precursor layers and Sb-Ge-Se thin films measured by EDX at 25 kV operation voltage. The data are shown in three groups corresponding to different Series 1, 2, and 3.

Sample	Se [mg]	T_{Se} [°C]	Sb [at %]	Ge [at %]	Se [at %]	[Sb]/[Ge]	[Se]/([Sb] + [Ge])
1_0	–	–	85.3	14.7	–	5.8	–
1_5	5	320	46.2	8.5	45.4	5.4	0.8
1_15	15	320	28.3	5.1	66.6	5.7	2.0
1_30	30	320	27.8	4.3	68.0	6.5	2.1
2_0	–	–	82.5	17.5	–	4.7	–
2_5	5	320	31.8	7.8	60.4	4.1	1.5
2_15	15	320	29.1	6.5	64.4	4.5	1.8
2_30	30	320	26.5	5.8	67.7	4.6	2.1
3_0	–	–	70.8	29.2	–	2.4	–
3_320	30	320	27.5	13.5	59.0	2.0	2.0
3_340	30	340	18.1	9.7	72.2	1.9	2.6

The significance of bold font used in Table 1 is to point out the number of the Series. Number_0 correspond to the Sb-Ge precursor layer before the selenization and it is the starting point of each Series of samples.

compared with the GeSe_2 phase that has a band gap energy near 2.96 eV.^[6]

The incorporation of Ge into the Sb chalcogenide materials leads to the replacement of Sb-X bonds with stronger Ge-X bonds ($X = \text{Se}, \text{S}$), a phenomenon that significantly alters the structural, optical, and electrical properties of the compound. The variation of $[\text{Sb}]/[\text{Ge}]$ and $[\text{S}]/[\text{Se}]$ atomic ratios will increase the bandgap energy E_g that guarantees the multiple applications of this semiconductor. The Sb-Ge chalcogenide material has been extensively studied as a phase change material (PCM). The principle of operation of chalcogenide PCMs relies on the fact that they can be rapidly and reversibly switched between two different solid phases, usually an amorphous and a crystalline state. This phase transition is accompanied by pronounced changes of the optical and electrical properties that can be easily detected. The combination of pronounced electrical-optical property changes and the ability to switch rapidly (nanosecond to femtosecond time scales) makes these materials attractive for a number of applications, ranging from rewritable optical data storage to nonvolatile electronic memories, photonic switches, and neuromorphic computing. These materials have been studied for decades; however, their interest has recently gained a new momentum due to their potential applications in emerging digital technologies that require enhanced control of optical properties and improved switching speeds.^[7] Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, despite their special electro-optical properties, the combinations of crystalline Sb-Ge chalcogenide semiconductors have not yet been incorporated in solar cell devices.

In this work, $(\text{GeSe}_2)_x(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}$ pseudo-binary system is fabricated by the selenization of co-evaporated Sb-Ge thin films. This work aims to achieve two primary objectives: 1) to investigate the composition, structural, morphological, vibrational, and optical properties of the synthesized Sb-Ge-Se thin films and 2) to demonstrate the successful fabrication and performance of PV devices based on these compounds. Our results show that both the incorporation of Se during the selenization process and the composition of the amorphous Sb-Ge precursor film are crucial to modify the band gap energy values, which range from 1.41 to 1.83 eV. Notably, for the first time, functional Sb-Ge-Se thin film solar cells are fabricated, providing a potential new application of

these chalcogenides. Furthermore, our work addresses several key features that are relevant for employing the Sb-Ge-Se compound in the development of new wide-band gap solar cells.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Sb-Ge-Se Thin Films: Effect of the Amount of Se Added

The initial phase of our work focused on assessing the impact of the incorporation of Se into the precursor layer during the thermal treatment at 320 °C. To achieve this, 5, 15, and 30 mg of elemental selenium were added to the graphite box along with the Sb-Ge samples corresponding to Series 1 and Series 2. The compositions of the Sb-Ge co-evaporated precursors and the chalcogenide thin films produced through various processes were probed using Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) measurements. **Table 1** presents the results obtained alongside the growth conditions. The primary difference between the two series is the evaporation rate of Sb, which was slightly reduced in Series 2. Notably, the higher $[\text{Sb}]/[\text{Ge}]$ atomic ratio in Series 1 samples is linked to the higher evaporation rate of Sb compared to Series 2. Additionally, we have also observed that a reduction in the concentration of added Se results in an increase in the concentrations of both Ge and Sb.

Figure S1, Supporting Information, shows the Grazing Incidence X-ray Diffraction (GIXRD) diffractograms and the cross-sectional SEM pictures of the Sb_2Se_3 and Ge-Se thin films used as references. Figure S1a, Supporting Information, illustrates that the GeSe_2 phase coexists with GeSe, with the diselenide phase being the predominant in the film. The main diffraction peaks corresponding to the orthorhombic Sb_2Se_3 phase (00-015-0861) and orthorhombic GeSe_2 phase (00-032-0410) are detected in the case of Sb and Ge chalcogenides, respectively. The calculated texture coefficients (TCs) from the XRD patterns of both chalcogenides are shown in Figure S2, Supporting Information. The TCs of most (hk1) planes become stronger for Sb_2Se_3 , which is advantageous for charge carrier transport and subsequently improves solar cell performance. Conversely, GeSe_2 exhibits a [020] orientation. The cross-sectional SEM image shown in Figure S1b, Supporting

Figure 1. Grazing incidence X-ray diffractograms of Sb-Ge-Se thin films corresponding to Series 1 with different Se amount added during the selenization process.

Information, shows the difference between the Sb_2Se_3 and 2D-Ge-Se layers deposited on Mo/SLG, revealing different features between the two materials. This observation leads to a critical question: what results from the combination of Sb and Ge chalcogenides through selenization of co-evaporated Sb-Ge layers?

Figure 1 shows GIXRD diffractograms of all the chalcogenide films corresponding to Series 1 by using a grazing incidence angle of 4° . Both Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 phases are detected. It is evident that the contribution of the GeSe_2 (00-032-0410) phase is higher when only 5 mg of Se is added during the selenization process, which is consistent with the increased Ge content measured by EDX (see Table 1). The Mo (00-042-1120) diffraction peak corresponding to the back contact is also detected, and the formation of MoSe_2 (04-004-8782) cannot be ruled out.

To further corroborate these findings, we conducted Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Sb_2Se_3 is known to be isomorphous to Sb_2S_3 with a primitive cell containing four Sb_2Se_3 units (20 atoms) and space group $Pnma$ (#62). The group analysis of the orthorhombic Sb_2Se_3 crystal in the Γ point of the Brillouin zone gives 60 different vibrational phonon modes. However, in the centrosymmetric $Pnma$ space group, asymmetrical vibrations will be IR active and Raman inactive, while symmetrical vibrations will be Raman active and IR inactive. Thus, Raman and IR modes will be mutually exclusive. Following the D_{2h}^{16} point group symmetry, the 60 vibrational modes are given as^[8] in equations (1), (2), (3) and (4):

$$\Gamma_{\text{IR}} = 9B_{2u} \otimes 4B_{1u} \otimes 9B_{3u} \quad (1)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{Raman}} = 10A_g \otimes 10B_{1g} \otimes 5B_{2g} \otimes 5B_{3g} \quad (2)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{acoustic}} = B_{1u} \otimes B_{2u} \otimes B_{3u} \quad (3)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{Silent}} = 5A_u \quad (4)$$

where 22 modes are IR active, 30 modes are Raman active, 3 are acoustic, and 5 are silent.

GeSe_2 crystallizes in the orthorhombic system with the symmetry D_{2h}^{13} and 24 atoms per unit cell. The factor group analysis at the center of the Brillouin zone yields^[9]

$$\Gamma_{\text{IR}} = 35A_u \otimes 34B_u \quad (5)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{Raman}} = 36A_g \otimes 36B_g \quad (6)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{acoustic}} = 1A_u \otimes 2B_u \quad (7)$$

where 72 modes are Raman active and 69 modes are IR active (see equations (5), (6) and (7)).

It is worth mentioning that FTIR bands have not been reported so far in the literature for these types of materials and it is used for the first time here to analyze the microstructure of the films and detect secondary phases that may form during the film's growth.

Several apparent peaks related to different phases in Series 1 can be seen in **Figure 2**. By comparing the FTIR absorbance spectra of the Sb-Ge-Se films with the ones measured in

Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 films, the coexistence of the two phases and the higher contribution of the GeSe_2 phase for lower Se added are both confirmed, in agreement with the GIXRD measurements. It is also clear from **Figure 2** that the contribution from the vibrational modes assigned to the Sb_2Se_3 phase are mainly observed in the far infrared range between 80 and 208 cm^{-1} , having B_{1u} and B_{2u} symmetry in agreement with previously reported modes measured using IR reflectivity.^[8] A shift of the main peak toward lower wavenumbers when increasing Se is observed, probably caused by the formation of elemental selenium phase and a change in the stoichiometry of the films during the selenization. This is emphasized by the presence of the peak at frequency 223 cm^{-1} assigned to the E vibrational mode of trigonal selenium,^[10] and the increase of its intensity observed here with increasing Se content. The shoulder on the low wavelength of the main peak at 179 cm^{-1} is assigned to antimony oxide Sb_2O_3 phase in accordance with the IR-active vibrational mode reported by Voit et al.,^[11] and related to the O-Sb-O wagging mode. In the spectral range between 260 and 340 cm^{-1} , the spectrum is dominated by a broad band consisting of overlapping several peaks that belong to the GeSe_2 phase.

Four apparent peaks related to GeSe_2 are observed with vibrational frequencies at $\sim 260, 273, 310, \text{ and } 336 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and are assigned to the A_u and B_u symmetry modes in accordance with the IR-active mode frequencies reported by Popovic et al.^[9]

In order to unveil all the overlapping and hidden peaks, deconvolution of the FTIR spectrum to Gaussian and Lorentzian peaks was done by simultaneously fitting the whole spectrum using the Voigt function. The results of the curve fitting together with the measurement data are displayed in **Figure 3**. The individual peaks fitting

Figure 2. FTIR measurements of Sb-Ge-Se thin films corresponding to Series 1 with different selenium content. FTIR spectra measured for Sb_2Se_3 and Ge-Se thin films are used as references for comparison.

related to the different phases are also shown in Figure 3, and these are Sb_2Se_3 (in blue), GeSe_2 (in green), Sb_2O_x (in purple), Se_n (in pink) and GeO_2 (in black). From the spectrum deconvolution, 30 peaks in total were resolved. From the 22 IR theoretically expected active modes in Sb_2Se_3 , 11 peaks are observed with symmetry modes B_{1u} and B_{2u} . The other 11 peaks related to the GeSe_2 phase and assigned to A_u and B_u symmetry modes are detected in all three principal directions. Symmetry modes assigned to both phases Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 in our FTIR measurements are in excellent agreement with previously reported data.^[8,9]

Peaks related to Se trigonal phase are observed in frequency modes $223\text{--}236\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and are in good agreement with the experimental IR vibrational modes reported by Lucovsky^[10] and Danielewicz.^[12] Two additional peaks belonging to α -monoclinic Se_8 phase are detected at frequencies 120 and 126 cm^{-1} and are assigned to B_2 doublet IR-active mode.

Additional peaks are observed at frequencies 180 and 214 cm^{-1} and are assigned to F_{2g} and E symmetry in Sb_2O_3 ^[11,13] and in $\alpha\text{-GeO}_2$ ^[14,15] phases, respectively, being both IR and Raman active modes.

The frequencies of all the found phases in Figure 3 are listed in Table 2, together with their tentative symmetry assignment and comparison with already published data.

Figure 3. Measured FTIR spectrum (open square) of sample 1_15 together with the cumulative fit (solid red line) using Voigt function. The peaks obtained from the deconvolution of the spectrum belonging to different phases are shown in different colors: Sb_2Se_3 (blue); GeSe_2 (green); Sb_2O_x (purple); Se_n (pink) and GeO_2 (dark). The difference between the measured data and the fitted one is also presented (orange line). Peaks numbers are in the order given in Table 2.

To characterize the near surface of the samples, we have employed the X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements. The composition of the samples of Series 1 obtained by XPS is given in Table 3. Comparison with results of Table 1 shows a Ge enrichment at the surface as compared to the bulk. In addition to that, the oxygen concentration increases upon decreasing the Se content during the selenization process.

In Figure 4, the overlapping Sb 4d and Ge 3d core level doublets are shown on the left, whereas the Se 3d core level doublet is shown on the right, for samples 1_5, 1_15, and 1_30, respectively, in black dotted lines. A complex shape of these core levels is observed, therefore indicating the contribution of several chemical species in the spectra. To reproduce the doublet of each chemical species, two peaks were used to account for the contribution of $d_{5/2}$ and $d_{3/2}$ core levels to the d doublets. A theoretical $d_{5/2}/d_{3/2}$ area ratio of 1.5 was imposed and a spin-orbit splitting of 0.6, 1.2, and 0.9 eV, for the Ge 3d, Sb 4d, and Se 3d, respectively, was used.^[16–19] According to Baudet et al.,^[16,17] the Ge 3d, Sb 4d, and Se 3d core levels were deconvoluted using the following chemical species: $\text{Ge}(\text{Se})_4$ in blue at 31.1 eV, $(\text{Ge,Sb})\text{-Ge}(\text{Se})_3$ in red at 30.6 eV, and $(\text{Se}_y)\text{-Ge-O}_x + \text{Ge-O}_x$ in green at 32.5 eV, for the Ge 3d signal; $\text{Sb}(\text{Se})_3$ in cyan at 33.6 eV, $(\text{Ge,Sb})\text{-Sb}(\text{Se})_2$ in magenta at 32.9 ± 0.1 eV, $(\text{Se}_y)\text{-Sb-O}_x$ in yellow at 34.6 eV, and $\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_5 + \text{Sb}_2\text{O}_4$ in orange at 35.3 eV, for the Sb 4d signal; $\text{Se-Se}(\text{Ge,Sb})$ in green at 54.7 eV, $(\text{Ge,Sb})\text{-Se}(\text{Ge,Sb})$ in red at 53.5 ± 0.1 eV, and $\text{Se}^0 + \text{SeO}_x$ in blue at 55.4 eV, for the Se 3d signal. The binding energy given for each chemical species corresponds to the maximum of the $d_{5/2}$ core level of the corresponding doublet. The fitted spectra are plotted in a continuous black line, whereas the contribution of each chemical species is plotted in continuous color lines.

$\text{Ge}(\text{Se})_4$ arrangement is related to Ge atoms bonded to four Se atoms corresponding to GeSe_2 tetrahedra. Likewise, $\text{Sb}(\text{Se})_3$

Table 2. IR-active modes frequencies obtained from analysis of the FTIR absorbance spectra shown in Figure 4 and their tentative symmetry assignments. Data taken from literature are shown for comparison.

Peak no.	This work				Literature	
	ω [cm ⁻¹]	<i>FWHM</i> [cm ⁻¹]	Phase	Sym.	ω [cm ⁻¹]	References
1	85.8	3.8	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	86	[8]
2	91.7	6.8	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	95	[8]
3	99.2	4.1	GeSe ₂	A _u	99	[9]
4	114.7	3.8	GeSe ₂	B _u	117	[9]
5	120.2	7.3	Se ₈	B ₂	116–122 doublet	[10]
6	126.4	4.0	Se ₈	B ₂	116–122 doublet	[10]
7	135.1	7.7	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	137	[8]
8	140.6	5.9	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{1u}	138	[8]
9	144.8	7.6	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	144	[8]
10	154.9	16.7	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{1u}	155	[8]
11	163.1	14.7	GeSe ₂	B _u	166	[9]
12	170.8	14.7	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	168	[8]
13	180.4	16.3	Sb ₂ O ₃	F _{2g} ^a	179	[11,13]
14	191.5	12.2	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{1u}	194	[8]
15	199.5	4.9	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	201	[8]
16	203.1	6.2	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	202	[8]
17	207.3	8.5	Sb ₂ Se ₃	B _{2u}	206	[8]
18	214.3	11.6	GeO ₂	E	212	[14,15]
19	218	5.4	GeSe ₂	B _u	216	[9]
20	223.6	7.0	Se	E ^a	225	[10]
21	226.7	5.3	Se	A ₁	226	[10]
22	230.7	7.5	Se	E ₂ ^a	231	[12]
23	236.6	5.1	Se	A ₂ + E	242	[12]
24	253.3	9.1	GeSe ₂	A _u	259	[9]
25	260	12.6	GeSe ₂	B _u	262	[9]
26	270.1	16.0	GeSe ₂	B _u	269	[9]
27	281	18.7	GeSe ₂	B _u	283	[9]
28	293.3	21.5	GeSe ₂	B _u	294	[9]
29	305.6	15.9	GeSe ₂	A _u	304	[9]
30	313.6	12.2	GeSe ₂	B _u	313	[9]

^aIndicates peaks that are both IR and Raman active.

arrangement is associated with Sb atoms bonded to three Se atoms corresponding to Sb₂Se₃ trigonal pyramids. When one Se atom is replaced by a Sb or Ge atom in the Ge-(Se)₄ and Sb-(Se)₃ arrangements, a distorted tetrahedron or a distorted trigonal pyramid is formed, respectively, and new (Ge,Sb)-Ge-(Se)₃ and (Ge,Sb)-Sb-(Se)₂ entities appear, therefore indicating some kind of structural disorder in the GeSe₂ and Sb₂Se₃ phases. Such changes are also reflected in the transformation of (Ge,Sb)-Se-(Ge,Sb) arrangements into Se-Se-(Ge,Sb). In addition to this, other mixed oxide species like (Se_γ)-Ge-O_x and (Se_γ)-Sb-O_x are observed. Moreover, the

Table 3. Composition of Sb-Ge-Se layers measured by XPS in samples of series 1.

Sample	Se [mg]	Sb [at %]	Ge [at %]	Se [at %]	O [at %]
1_5	5	7.6	35.5	21.9	35.0
1_15	15	13.3	21.5	37.4	27.8
1_30	30	9.3	19.0	46.9	24.8

formation of species related to the presence of Ge and Se suboxides Ge-O_x and Se-O_x, respectively, and Sb₂O₅ and/or Sb₂O₄ oxides, along with the presence of elemental Se species, Se⁰, cannot be discarded,^[18,19] in agreement with FTIR measurements of Figures 2 and 3. The percentage of the different chemical species of Ge, Sb, and Se is given in Table S1, Supporting Information.

Raman scattering measurements at T = 300 K obtained from samples belonging to Series 1, 1_5, 1_15, and 1_30 are presented in Figure 5a using green solid lines. For comparison, the spectra of pure GeSe₂ and Sb₂Se₃ obtained using the same experimental setup and under the same experimental conditions are presented underneath the Ge-Se and Sb₂Se₃ thin films' spectra in Figure 5 as dashed red and blue lines, respectively. Their Raman intensities are relative and are used for qualitative comparison only.

As illustrated in Figure 5a, the thin film spectra are dominated by the lattice vibrations of Sb₂Se₃. Though much lower in intensity, the contributions from GeSe₂ compound are also readily apparent in our spectra (mainly the characteristic GeSe₂ peak positioned at about 211 cm⁻¹^[20,21]). Additionally, there are various peaks (127.0, 224.9, 230.6, 236.9 and 260.8 cm⁻¹) in the spectra that can be attributed to the Sb₂O_{x=3,4} layer forming on top of the films,^[21] typically observed in Raman spectra of Sb₂Se₃ single crystals.^[22] Comparing the spectra of three Sb-Ge-Se thin film samples, it is evident that the GeSe₂ contributions are the highest for thin film obtained by adding 5 mg Se during the thermal treatment, confirming the richer Ge composition of thin film Sample 1_5, which is in agreement with the GIXRD and FTIR measurements.

To estimate the corresponding contributions of Sb₂Se₃, GeSe₂, and Sb₂O_x in the spectra, we fitted the experimental data using the cumulative fit consisting of multiple Voigt line profiles superimposed on top of the electronic continuum modeled using a simple model including a damped Lorentzian and linear term,^[23] (see equation (8)):

$$R' \chi(\omega, T) = a(T) \cdot \omega / (\omega^2 + \Gamma(T)^2) + b(T) \cdot \omega. \quad (8)$$

To achieve better control over the fit, the energies of the modes were initially fixed to match the previously reported values of Sb₂Se₃,^[22,24–26] GeSe₂^[20] and Sb₂O_x^[21] phonon modes. We first fitted the spectra of the pure compounds, and the obtained values were used as the initial parameters for the cumulative fitting of the spectra of the films. Due to the finite resolution of our spectrometer, we were able to resolve 32 Raman peaks. The contribution from each mode to the cumulative fit together with the resulting cumulative fit is presented in Figure 5b and compiled in a list given in Table S2, Supporting Information.

As shown above, the coexistence of Sb₂Se₃ and GeSe₂ phases is confirmed by different techniques. These results indicate that the presence of Sb₂Se₃ promotes the formation of the GeSe₂ phase, with an almost complete absence of the Ge-Se phase. The selenization of the Ge layer

Figure 4. Overlapping Sb 4d and Ge 3d core level doublets on the left, and Se 3d core level doublet on the right, for samples 1_5, 1_15 and 1_30, respectively, in black dotted lines. Spectra are deconvoluted as explained in the text.

evinces the need to increase the selenization temperature up to at least 400 °C to minimize the presence of the Ge-Se phase, as illustrated in Figure S1a, Supporting Information.

Figure 6 shows the cross-sectional Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) picture of $(\text{GeSe}_2)_x(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}$ samples corresponding to Series 1. All Sb-Ge-Se layers are compact and free of pinholes, exhibiting no adhesion issues with the Mo back contact; however, they display distinct features. The increase in the Sb-Ge-Se thickness with the addition of Se is reflected in the formation of a thin layer of smaller grains at the Sb-Ge-Se/Mo back interface. This layer's thickness increases from approximately 140 to 200 nm with the incorporation of 15 mg

and 30 mg of Se, respectively. EDX mapping of these structures (Figure 6e,f) reveals the accumulation of Se near the Mo contact, corresponding to the thin layer with smaller grains. The mappings also show a decrease in Ge content as the concentration of Se added during the thermal treatment increases. Sample 1_30 is characterized by a more defined and crystalline structure, similar to that of Sb_2Se_3 (see Figure S1b, Supporting Information). Even though the XRD pattern, FTIR, and Raman spectroscopies did not rule out the occurrence of the GeSe_2 crystalline phase for that absorber layer, the growth of GeSe_2 crystals could not be followed by SEM, due to the faster nucleation and growth of Sb_2Se_3 that completely overgrew the sample.^[27] While the EDX results obtained from the same sample indicate a 4% concentration of Ge in the films, it is unlikely that this can be primarily attributed to the GeSe_2 phase, given the very low selenization temperature of 320 °C, which is insufficient for the formation of a well-defined crystalline phase of GeSe_2 . J. Barták et al.^[27] reported that it was possible to simultaneously follow the growth of Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 crystals in the $(\text{GeSe}_2)_{0.7}(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3)_{0.3}$ composition, but not for lower x in the $(\text{GeSe}_2)_x(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}$ system. We report in this work a considerably lower Ge content in the absorbers. Unlike sample 1_30, the EDX mapping of sample 1_5 mg Se shows a bilayer structure with the accumulation of Sb and Se near the Mo back contact and of Ge and Se near the surface. The concentration of [Ge] in this sample is more than twice that found in sample 1_30 mg Se (see Table 1).

The reduced evaporation rate of Sb results in the Sb-Ge-Se films with a lower [Sb]/[Ge] atomic ratio for Series 2 (see Table 1). Samples of Series 2 exhibit the same behavior as that observed in Series 1. Specifically, a higher presence of GeSe_2 in Sb-Ge-Se thin films when 5 mg of Se is added during the thermal treatment—compared to samples with 15 and 30 mg Se concentrations—as observed also in the Raman spectra corresponding to Series 2 shown in Figure 5c.

The cross-sectional SEM pictures and EDX mappings of the Sb-Ge precursor layer and the chalcogenides, obtained using different amounts of elemental selenium in Series 2 samples, can be found in Figure 7. The co-evaporation of Sb and Ge without heating the substrate results in an Sb-Ge amorphous structure of 200 nm thickness with a uniform distribution of Sb and Ge throughout the precursor film (see Figure 7a,e). However, the addition of 5 mg Se at 320 °C results in the formation of a bilayer structure, also observed in Series 1 (see Figure 7f). It is noteworthy that a higher accumulation of both Ge and Se is observed at the surface. This indicates that the amount of Se added was insufficient to fully diffuse through the layer thickness at a temperature of 320 °C. However, increasing the Se content during the

Figure 5. a) Raman spectra of Sample 1_5, 1_15 and 1_30. Blue and red vertical lines are added to indicate the characteristic modes of pure Sb_2Se_3 and $GeSe_2$, respectively. b) Cumulative fit of the experimental data of Sample 1_30 (green solid line) consisting of electronic continuum (dark red line), modeled utilizing a damped Lorentzian and linear term, and 32 phonon modes (whose values are extracted from the literature) fitted using Voigt profiles.^[20–26] The contribution from each mode to the cumulative fit is presented using blue (Sb_2Se_3), red ($GeSe_2$) and purple (Sb_2O_x) solid lines. c) Raman spectra of Sample 2_5, 2_15 and 2_30 measured in parallel polarization configuration at $T = 300$ K. Spectra of pure Sb_2Se_3 and $GeSe_2$ compounds scaled for clarity are given as dashed blue and red line, respectively.

Figure 6. Cross-sectional SEM pictures and EDX mapping of Sb-Ge-Se films grown on Mo/SLG corresponding to Series 1: a, d) 1_5 mg Se, b, e) 1_15 mg Se and c, f) 1_30 mg Se.

Figure 7. a, e) Cross-sectional SEM pictures and EDX mapping of Sb-Ge precursor film; and of Sb-Ge-Se films grown on Mo/SLG corresponding to Series 2: b, f) 2_5 mg Se, c, g) 2_15 mg Se and d, h) 2_30 mg Se.

selenization process results in a more uniform distribution of all elements throughout the chalcogenide layer and enhances the crystalline quality. Different from Series 1, the incorporation of additional Se does not cause the formation of the thin layer of small grains at the back interface. As indicated earlier, the structure of Sb-Ge-Se samples, especially those produced by adding 30 mg Se during the thermal treatment, resembles the structure of Sb_2Se_3 . This behavior is anticipated due to the considerably higher concentration of Sb relative to Ge in all the investigated samples and the selenization temperature used.

To ascertain a more detailed study on the distribution of the elements inside the films, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis was performed on sample 2_30 mg Se. **Figure 8** shows a High-Angle Annular Dark-Field-Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (HAADF-STEM) image (Figure 8a) and the corresponding STEM-coupled energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) elemental mapping of the cross section of the sample 2_30 mg Se together with a colormix map (Figure 8b), where the interaction between elements can be deduced. The EDX elemental maps of Ge (Figure 8d), Se (Figure 8e) and Sb (Figure 8f) are also indicated using different color fonts. Additionally, we performed an averaged line scan profile along the layer, starting from the bottom Mo (marked with an arrow and rectangle in Figure 8b) to obtain the atomic fraction distribution (Figure 8c). Based on the atomic fraction quantification, areas containing 40% Sb and 60% Se were identified, which correspond to Sb_2Se_3 grains. No Ge was detected in these regions, which are highlighted in pink in **Figure 9b** and attributed to the mixing of Sb (red) and Se

(blue). However, regions with a 15% of Ge and 75% of Se with a Sb background around 4% are detected, corresponding to the orange areas in **Figure 8b** as a result of Se (red) and Ge (yellow). These elements distribution can also be deduced from the average line scan of **Figure 8c**. In all the analyzed areas, the Ge-rich regions are surrounding the Sb_2Se_3 crystals and are also near the Mo back contact, where less Sb is present. Besides the significant cross-diffusion between Mo and Se observed in **Figure 8c**, Se content increases faster and sooner than the Ge content near the Mo/active layer interface, as it was previously reported for Se and Sb in Sb_2Se_3 layers.^[28]

In **Figure 9**, the absorption coefficient of the samples 1_5, 1_30, and 2_30 grown on SLG substrates versus photon energy is shown, as obtained from the ellipsometry measurements. Here, an indirect band gap energy was estimated from Tauc's plots. It is clear from Series 1 that the band gap energy of $(\text{GeSe}_2)_x(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}$ samples decreases when more Se is added during the selenization process, from 1.61 to 1.41 eV for 5 mg Se and 30 mg Se, respectively. This observation is consistent with the reduced concentration of Ge in the sample with 30 mg of Se, suggesting that the increase in the band gap energy can be attributed to a higher presence of GeSe_2 . The sample 2_30 has an even higher band gap energy of 1.69 eV. This can be linked to the much richer concentration of Ge in the precursor film of Series 2 samples. Therefore, we believe that the band gap energy of the Sb-Ge-Se system can be effectively tailored via the modification of the composition of the co-evaporated Sb-Ge precursor film and the Se incorporation during the selenization process. The band gap values obtained here are

Figure 8. Cross-sectional STEM pictures and EDX mapping of sample 2_30 mg Se. a) HAADF-STEM, b) color mix for Ge, Se, Mo and Sb, c) atomic fraction of the averaged line scan profile marked with a white arrow and rectangle in (b), d) Ge atomic quantification map, e) Se atomic quantification map and f) Sb atomic quantification map.

Figure 9. Absorption coefficient versus photon energy of Sb-Ge-Se thin films produced by selenization of co-evaporated Sb-Ge layers and the optical band gap energy as determined from the Tauc's plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs $h\nu$.

higher than the expected ones related to Ge content, reported in the literature.^[29,30] However, our Sb-Ge-Se thin films are completely different from those reported in,^[29,30] being characterized by a non-uniform in-depth distribution of the elements and the presence of Sb and Ge oxides.

2.2. Sb-Ge-Se Thin Films: Selenization Temperature

So far, it is established that a Ge-rich precursor film along with the supply of 30 mg of Se during the selenization process resulted in an enhanced structure and a uniform distribution of the elements through the chalcogenide layer. A new Series 3 was prepared with a much slower Sb evaporation rate resulting in Sb-poor precursor

samples, as it is shown in Table 1. Here, we analyze the influence of Se temperature of 320 and 340 °C during the 30 min long selenization process. In both cases, 30 mg of Se was supplied during the thermal treatment. As expected, a higher Se temperature leads to a higher Se concentration in the film, and, consequently, to lower Sb and Ge contents. FTIR measurements of Sb-Ge-Se thin films treated at 340 °C (Figure S3, Supporting Information) show the coexistence of Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 phases, as well as the presence of Sb_2O_4 , GeO_2 , and Se_6 phases. Regardless of the amount of Se added and the maximum temperature used during the selenization process, the coexistence of Sb and Ge chalcogenides, along with oxide phases and Se, is always observed.

Cross-sectional SEM pictures and EDX mappings of the Sb-Ge-Se thin films produced by selenization at 320 and 340 °C are shown in Figure 10. There is a clear correlation between the increase in the selenization temperature and the increase of the film thickness. The accumulation of Ge at the top surface of the film occurs independently of the selenization temperature, resulting in a bilayer structure. Also, a higher Se content is detected in the sample selenized at

Figure 10. Cross-sectional SEM picture and EDX mappings of Sb-Ge-Se thin films selenized at a, c) 320 °C, and b, d) 340 °C.

Figure 11. a) J-V curves and b) EQE measurements of the best solar cells of Series 1, 2 and 3. c) DLCP and C-V measurements of the best Sb-Ge-Se and reference Sb_2Se_3 solar cells.

difference in the band gaps of samples selenized at 320 and 340 °C, this variation is attributed to the lower Ge content rather than the temperature itself.

2.3. Sb-Ge-Se Thin Film Solar Cells

As previously mentioned, these materials have been employed in a range of applications, including optical information storage and sensors. However, to the best of our knowledge, they have not yet been explored for use in PV applications. We report in the present work the first successful fabrication of solar cells based on Sb-Ge-Se thin films. The current density-voltage (J-V) curves of the best Sb-Ge-Se-based solar cells prepared using the absorber layers corresponding to Series 1, 2, and 3 are shown in **Figure 11a**. The PV parameters of these samples are summarized in **Table 4**. Although the efficiency reported here is not particularly high, it is nonetheless comparable to the early performance reported in other emerging materials when they were introduced for the first time.^[31–33]

The fabrication of certain PV devices based on Sb-Ge-Se was not finalized as some samples were delaminated after the CdS deposition. This issue was observed specifically in the samples with higher Ge content for each series. Thus, the best Sb-Ge-Se PV devices were those with 30 mg Se corresponding to Series 1 and 2. The higher efficiencies of these solar cells are attributed to the high short-circuit current density (J_{SC}), which aligns with the higher external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements across the entire wavelength range (see **Figure 11b**). A lower series resistance R_{s} is also reported in 1_30 and 2_30 solar cells

Table 4. PV parameters of the different Sb-Ge-Se thin film solar cells investigated in this work. A reference Sb_2Se_3 solar cell is added for comparison.

Device	V_{OC} [mV]	J_{SC} [mA cm^{-2}] [ta/aa]	FF [%]	η [%] [ta/aa]	R_{s} [$\Omega\text{-cm}^2$]	R_{sh} [$\Omega\text{-cm}^2$]
1_30	356	4.2/9.7	35.9	0.50/1.20	8.3	235.2
2_30	299	10.6/11.4	39.4	1.25/1.34	9.6	102.6
2_15	426	3.9/0.8	39.4	0.65/0.14	19.8	230.3
3_340	307	2.4/1.7	32.0	0.23/0.17	42.5	195.0
Sb_2Se_3	411	20.1/25.3	51.6	4.3/5.4	5.2	260.2

aa, active area as determined by EQE measurements; ta, total area as determined from J-V curves.

with higher J_{SC} . As shown in **Table 1**, samples 1_30 and 2_30 have the lowest Ge concentrations, with sample 2_30 exhibiting a slightly higher concentration than sample 1_30. The higher EQE at the short wavelength for sample 2_30 indicates that a different CdS/(Sb-Ge-Se) interface is formed despite the same CdS layer deposition. The main difference between both active layers is the microstructure and the elements distribution through the Sb-Ge-Se layer. While sample 2_30 shows a uniform distribution of the elements, sample 1_30 is characterized by a thin layer of small grains at the (Sb-Ge-Se)/Mo back interface associated with an excess of Se. The uniform structure of 2_30 can be the reason for the enhanced J_{SC} with improved carrier transport. The best device, 2_30, achieves an active area efficiency of 1.34%, which is mainly limited by the low open circuit voltage V_{OC} due to the lowest shunt resistance R_{sh} . The FF is notably low for all analyzed samples, particularly for the 3_340 device, which exhibits a significantly high R_{s} . The most significant reduction of the device performance with much lower FF and J_{SC} is reported in samples with higher Ge content. As shown in **Figure 10**, the bilayer structure exhibits a significant accumulation of Ge-Se at the top of the absorber layer, with the presence of Sb_2Se_3 only around the Mo back contact. This distribution differs from that observed in the 1_30 and 2_30 solar cells, which were produced using the same selenization process. This unique structural characteristic can be responsible for the low short-circuit current density that hinders the collection of the charge carriers. Therefore, we cannot conclude that Ge content is the only parameter that controls the device performance, but also the elements distribution through the active layer. The discrepancy between the integrated J_{SC} from the EQE and the obtained from the J-V curves is quite intriguing. The integrated J_{SC} is lower than that obtained from J-V curve analysis for the samples with a higher Ge concentration and higher presence of GeSe_2 , devices 2_15 and 3_340. Becerril-Romero et al.^[34] claimed that this behavior indicates the presence of charged defects that affect collection during low-light-intensity EQE measurements, but are partially neutralized by photogenerated carriers under more intense illumination in J-V curve acquisition. The reason for this discrepancy could also be the presence of micro shunts caused by the GeSe_2 secondary phases. When the cell is illuminated on a small area (like for EQE measurement) the parts that are not illuminated behave as shunting load allowing the current to be drained through them. In **Table 4**, the PV parameters of Sb_2Se_3 solar cell, fabricated by the same method, are added for comparison. As can be seen, we have achieved significantly higher J_{SC} and FF values. As investigated by XPS, the lower Se content the higher oxygen concentration is in the films. It is known that the formation of Sb_2O_3 is detrimental for

the device performance, mainly affecting J_{SC} , serving as recombination centers in Sb_2Se_3 -based thin film solar cells.^[35,36] GeO_2 and Se_n secondary phases are most likely increasing the parasitic resistance effect in the devices and therefore reducing the device performance. The Sb-Ge-Se PV devices have high series resistance and low shunt resistance. While high series resistance may be caused by the presence of the secondary phases at the interface which act as interface recombination, low shunt resistance is mainly caused by the presence of the secondary phases in the bulk.^[37] Sb_2Se_3 solar cell also presents a much higher EQE in the whole wavelength range, which agrees with the much higher J_{SC} (see Table 4). Therefore, the uncontrolled incorporation of Ge leads to a deterioration of the PV devices.

Capacitance-Voltage (C-V) and Drive-Level Capacitance Profiling (DLCP) measurements of the best Sb-Ge-Se solar cell, 2_30, are shown in Figure 11c. Generally, C-V characteristics represent the response of interface defects, bulk defects, and free carriers, while DLCP measurements reflect the response of bulk defects and free carriers. Thus, the discrepancy at zero bias between the apparent density from CV measurements (N_{CV}) and the one from DLCP measurements (N_{DLCP}) is connected to interface defect density (N_i). The depletion width is $W_d = 138$ nm and $N_{CV} = 5.1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The similar depth profiles observed in C-V and DLCP indicate that the (Sb-Ge-Se)/CdS interface does not present a major issue. However, bulk defects remain significant, even with a uniform compact structure of the absorber material. C-V and DLCP measurements were also performed on the reference

solar cell Sb_2Se_3 , showing a wider $W_d = 175$ nm, which indicates a higher depletion region in the Sb_2Se_3 absorber and better charge carriers' collection that agrees well with the higher J_{SC} . In addition, lower $N_{DLCP} = 1.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $N_{CV} = 7.9 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ are obtained with $N_i = 5.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This is an indication that the $(GeSe_2)_x(Sb_2Se_3)_{1-x}$ system is more defective than the Sb_2Se_3 material. However, as mentioned above and shown in Figure 11c, the C-V and DLCP profiles of Sb-Ge-Se solar cells are very similar. This leads us to consider the nature of the (Sb-Ge-Se)/CdS heterointerface. A thorough defects analysis ought to be undertaken after the quality of the absorber layer and the structural design of the devices have been improved. Such in-depth analysis will assist in identifying the key factors that could be implemented to boost the solar cell efficiency. To examine the quality of the (Sb-Ge-Se)/CdS heterointerface, TEM measurements were performed on the best solar cell, sample 2_30 mg, (see Figure 12).

Figure 12a shows a HAADF-STEM image and the colormix map of all the elements displayed in Figure 12b, where the Zn (ZnO layer) and the In (ITO layer) are clearly identified. For better understanding, an average line scan profile along the layer starting from the bottom Mo (marked with an arrow and rectangle in Figure 12b) is shown in Figure 12c. Figure S4, Supporting Information, shows the corresponding STEM-coupled EDX elemental maps for Se, Sb, Cd, and S. The first significant result is the absence of Ge-Se-Sb regions in these devices, contrary to the results previously observed in EDX and also in both SEM (see Figure 7) and STEM (see Figure 8). In order to have a deeper

Figure 12. Cross-sectional STEM pictures and EDX mapping of sample 2_30 mg Se solar cell. a) gathers the HAADF-STEM; b) colormix map for S, Zn, Se, Mo, Cd, In and Sb; c) atomic fraction of the linear scan profile marked with a white arrow in (b); d) HAADF-STEM of the back interface at a higher magnification; e) atomic fraction of the linear scan profile marked with a white arrow in (d) which shows a detailed elements distribution at the active layer/Mo interface. a) and the corresponding EDX maps b) carried out at a magnification of 65 k while d) at a magnification of 130 k.

understanding of this empirical observation, a more detailed analysis of the interface was carried out at a higher magnification (Figure 12d). Following the same procedure as before, an average line scan starting from the Mo (marked with an arrow and rectangle in Figure 12d) was carried out, as shown in Figure 12e. For clearer display of the data, the profile of the Ge atomic fraction (purple) is represented on the secondary y-axis. The data reveal that the finalization of the solar cell leads to a very different distribution of Ge element with a very low content concentrated near the Mo back contact together with an enhancement of Se. In fact, these measurements allow us to determine the formation of a MoSe₂ layer of 30–50 nm at the interface as reported in.^[28]

More compelling is the diffusion of Cd and S into the active layer, surrounding the Sb-Se crystals, as evidenced by the atomic fraction maps and the profiles shown in Figure 12 and Figure S4, Supporting Information. While Sb₂Se₃/CdS forms a planar heterojunction as we investigated and shown in the literature^[28] a very different structure is developed for this Sb-Ge-Se PV device, similar to that observed in other organic and perovskite solar cells^[38] which can be responsible for a working PV device and the similar C-V and DLCP profiles.

These experimental results seem to indicate that Ge selenide is partly dissolved and removed during the CdS chemical bath at 70 °C, which can be expected due to the more amorphous GeSe₂ phase than the well-crystalline Sb₂Se₃. While the maximum Ge content measured in the completed device is near 2 at %, the Ge concentration in the sample 2_30 is almost 6 at %, as shown in Table 1. The considerably lower Ge content can elucidate the lower E_g extracted from the EQE measurements in Figure 11b, compared to those obtained by the optical characterization of the absorber layer (see Figure 9). However, the introduction of a passivation layer at the (Sb-Ge-Se)/CdS interface may be a crucial factor for enhancing carrier transport, as demonstrated by Liu et al.^[5] in their study of GeSe-based solar cells. They reported a significant improvement in Ge-Se superstrate solar cell performance by incorporating a 10 nm thick Sb₂Se₃ passivation layer between the CdS and Ge-Se layers. This passivation layer resulted in a substantial increase in efficiency, from 1.4% to 5.2%, by enhancing the buffer/absorber interface.

These results suggest that it is necessary to explore the variation of absorber thickness, alternative thermal treatments, and doping levels, among other factors, to enhance the device performance.

It is known that long-term stability testing is crucial for assessing the reliability of the material system in real-world applications. Therefore, a preliminary stability evaluation was performed on the device with the best photovoltaic performance, corresponding to sample 2_30, which was stored in ambient air for 1 year. The efficiency recorded on 15 cells, when the sample was freshly prepared and after storage, is shown in Figure 13. These results reveal that the device presents a good stability even after 1 year of storage in ambient air, unveiling the potential of the newly developed materials as promising candidates for photovoltaic applications, owing not only to their earth-abundant and non-toxic nature but also to a sustained stability over time. Further investigations should be focused on studying the degradation process under different aging conditions, after state-of-the-art devices are developed, to assess issues related to long-term illumination and high-temperature exposure.

3. Conclusions

Sb-Ge-Se thin films were successfully deposited by selenization of co-evaporated Sb-Ge layers on Mo/SLG and SLG substrates with different

Figure 13. Interval plot of efficiency in sample 2–30 (15 cells in total), measured in fresh sample and after 1 year of storage in ambient air.

[Sb]/[Ge] atomic ratios. The influence of Se content added during the selenization process was investigated by probing the structural, compositional, morphological, vibrational, and optical properties of the Sb-rich chalcogenides with [Sb]/[Ge] atomic ratios in the range from 6.5 to 4.1.

The coexistence of Sb₂Se₃ and GeSe₂ phases is confirmed in all films by GIXRD, XPS, Raman spectroscopy, and FTIR measurements. Notably, the formation of GeSe₂ is correlated with lower Se incorporation, while crystalline Sb₂Se₃ forms at low selenization temperature of 320 °C. Additional phases including Ge and Sb oxides, as well as Se⁰ are identified.

The lower Se supply of 5 mg during the selenization process leads to the formation of films characterized by a bilayer structure, featuring a Ge-Se layer at the surface and an Sb-Se layer located near the Mo back contact. The increase of Se content up to 30 mg promotes a more uniform distribution of the elements across the Sb-Ge-Se film, as indicated by EDX mapping in SEM. Conversely, TEM images reveal significant accumulation of Ge around the Sb₂Se₃ crystals.

The properties of the Sb-Ge-Se system can be gradually tailored in terms of band gap energy by modifying the composition of the co-evaporated Sb-Ge precursor layers and adjusting the Se incorporation during the selenization process, resulting in band gap energies E_g that vary from 1.41 to 1.69 eV.

Once the addition of Se (30 mg) is optimized, Sb-poor chalcogenides with [Sb]/[Ge] ~ 2.0 are fabricated at selenization temperatures of 320 and 340 °C. The coexistence of both Sb₂Se₃ and GeSe₂ phases is detected, as well as the formation of the bilayer structure with a thicker Ge-Se top layer. This bilayer structure is formed independently of the selenization temperature. The higher Ge concentration of 13.5% in the Sb-Ge-Se system increases the band gap E_g to 1.83 eV.

To highlight the potential use of these Sb-Ge-Se thin films in PV applications, solar cells are fabricated for the first time using Sb₂₆Ge₆Se₆₈ as an absorber layer and SLG/Mo/Sb-Ge-Se/CdS/ZnO/ITO stack configuration, achieving an overall efficiency of 1.25% (1.34% in active area). Higher defect densities N_{CV} and N_{DLCP} and shorter depletion width W_d are obtained for this device compared to Sb₂Se₃-based solar cells fabricated using the same method and structure. This is an indication that the (GeSe₂)_x(Sb₂Se₃)_{1-x} system is more defective than Sb₂Se₃

material. Cross-sectional STEM and EDX mapping of the completed PV device reveal that Ge selenide is partially dissolved and removed during the CdS chemical bath deposition due to its amorphous structure, in contrast to the well-crystalline Sb_2Se_3 . Notably, Cd and S diffuse into the active layer, surrounding the Sb-Se crystals and forming a distinct (Sb-Ge-Se)/CdS heterojunction. This indicates that refining the hetero-interface between the buffer and the absorber layer is also crucial for enhancing solar cell performance. In terms of experimental perspective, it is necessary to develop strategies to enhance the hetero-interface while maintaining the Ge concentration in the $(\text{GeSe}_2)_x(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}$ system, as this is crucial for the performance enhancement of wide-band gap material devices. The preliminary degradation evaluation shows that the Sb-Ge-Se-based solar cells maintain impressive long-term stability after 1 year of exposure to ambient air, accentuating their potential as abundant, non-toxic, and stable materials for photovoltaic applications.

4. Experimental Section

Sb-Ge chalcogenide fabrication: Sb-Ge-Se thin films were grown by selenization of co-evaporated Sb-Ge thin films. Sb-Ge thin films were co-evaporated from Sb and Ge sources at room substrate temperature. The base pressure in the vacuum chamber was $\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar, while the working pressure was in the range of 10^{-6} mbar. The [Sb]/[Ge] atomic ratio was controlled by the evaporation rate of the Sb layer, varying from 1 to 0.5 \AA s^{-1} . The Sb-Ge precursor layers were placed into a graphite box inside a tubular furnace and selenized for 30 min under an Ar atmosphere. In addition, Sb_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 were also fabricated by the selenization of Sb and Ge layers so that they could be used as reference samples to compare with the Sb-Ge-Se system. The selenization of Sb and Ge was carried out at 340 and 400 °C, respectively.

Device fabrication: A CdS buffer layer of around 50 nm thickness was grown by chemical bath at 70 °C for 8 min. A window layer composed of i-ZnO (50 nm) and $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{SnO}_2$ (ITO) (350 nm) layers was deposited by DC-pulsed sputtering deposition. Neither grids nor an anti-reflection coating were deposited onto the final photovoltaic devices. Moreover, no thermal treatment was performed on the solar cells.

Characterization: Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) (Oxford instruments, model INCAx-sight) using a Hitachi S-3000N scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to measure the chemical composition of the Sb-Ge-Se thin films. For that, operating voltages of 25 kV and the Sb L, Ge K, and Se K lines were employed for elemental quantification. Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) was performed to study the structural properties of the chalcogenide thin films and to identify the different phases. GIXRD data were collected with a PANalytical X'Pert Pro MPD diffractometer, using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and a multi-layer mirror to produce a parallel beam. Detector scans with an incident angle of 4° were carried out. The morphology of the Sb-Ge-Se/Mo/glass structure was analyzed by SEM using a SEM FEI VERIOS 460, operating at 2 kV. Elemental EDX mapping of the Sb-Ge-Se/Mo structure was performed at a lower operating voltage of 5 kV using an Octane Plus detector connected to the SEM. Cross-sectional specimens suitable for high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) characterization were prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB) Helios 600 dual-beam system and examined in a Talos F200X field emission TEM/STEM operating at 200 keV with four symmetrical EDX detectors. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were done in an ultra-high vacuum chamber using a hemispherical analyzer (SPECS Phoibos 100MCD-5) and Al K α (1486.6 eV) radiation from a twin anode (Al-Mg) X-ray source at a constant power of 300 W. Raman scattering measurements of the chalcogenide layers were carried out using a JY T64000 triple Raman system with the 1800/1800/1800 grooves mm^{-1} in backscattering micro-Raman configuration. The 514.5 nm line of a mixed Ar+/Kr+ gas laser was used as an excitation source. Laser-beam focusing is achieved through the Olympus objective with 0.8 NA and 50 \times magnification. The laser power was restricted to a maximum of 0.7 mW, and the laser spot size was approximately 5 μm . The spectral position was calibrated by using the main phonon peak at 520 cm^{-1} of a bulk monocrystalline Si wafer as a reference. Measurements were performed at room temperature and in open air in both parallel

and crossed polarization configurations, with a data acquisition time of 15 min and 10 accumulations per spectrum. Fourier Transform Infrared measurements were performed using a Bruker Vertex 80 V spectrometer. The data were recorded in reflectance then converted into absorbance spectra using Kubelka-Munk conversion. The optical bandgap was determined from the absorption coefficient spectra as determined from the analysis and fit of variable angle spectroscopic ellipsometry data measured in the VIS–NIR spectral range from 250 to 1700 nm with a wavelength step of 10 nm, at angles of incidence 60, 65, and 70° using a VASE Woollam ellipsometer.^[39]

Current–Voltage (*I*-*V*) characteristics of the photovoltaic devices were measured by using a Sun 3000 class solar simulator (Abet Technologies Inc., Milford, Connecticut, USA) under standard test conditions (25 °C, AM 1.5, 100 mW cm^{-2}). External quantum efficiency (EQE) of the solar cells was measured using a Bentham PVE300 system (Bentham Instruments Ltd, Berkshire, UK) calibrated with a Si and Ge photodiodes. C-V and DLCP measurements were performed using a HP 4192A LF impedance analyzer (5 Hz–13 MHz) at a frequency $f = 100 \text{ kHz}$.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Keywords

chalcogenides, Sb-Ge-Se, selenization, solar cells

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